

**IMPROVING THE URBAN ROAD IMPROVEMENT SYSTEM AND
IMPROVING THE LANDSCAPE**

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Abstract: The traffic service system, together with tools and design, constitutes a complex of facilities and facilities that allow to improve the road, that is, to ensure the normal living conditions of people using the roads and to ensure the functional capabilities of transport.

Key words: landscape, landscaping, landscaping, road, methods, standards, plants.

Methods and standards for improving the system of street and road beautification and landscape improvement in Uzbekistan will be discussed. Recommendations for further improvement are given. Seedlings on the streets belong to the general use category. Since city dwellers spend most of their time on the streets, optimal sanitation (shading of roads and sidewalks, protection of passers-by and adjacent areas from dust, gas, road noise) and aesthetic creating conditions is an urgent task.

In Uzbekistan, the highway and street beautification program [1] was adopted, it was planned to plant 1.6 million trees and shrubs along highways, 782 thousand on city streets, including more than 103 thousand trees and bushes in Tashkent. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan [2] "On measures to improve the system of highway improvement and architecture-landscape design", increasing the level of architectural-artistic design of highways, on measures to increase the level of design, improvement of the road improvement and improvement system [2] in close connection with the modern requirements of ensuring road safety and environmental protection, the republican automobile placement of green areas along the roads and a systematic and comprehensive approach to the beautification of roadside strips. Landscape plants (shrubs, conifers, medium and tall trees) are listed.

Improvement of streets and roads, as we mentioned above, should be carried out in a single complex and with a master development plan. When planning landscaping, it is necessary to take into account underground and surface communications and structures, take into account the prospects of possible changes in the future (widening of streets, additions, etc.), so that corrections can be made if necessary. The appearance of seedlings is easily done. The development and beautification of urban areas directly depends on the purpose and width of streets and roads, the intensity of traffic and the nature of the surrounding buildings (size of buildings, architectural design, etc.) [3]. The main types of plantings: rows and bushes, groups, strips of trees and bushes, lawns (Fig. 1.a), herbaceous flowering plants in vases and containers (Fig. 1.b), etc. The main types of seedlings (Fig. 1.c). Plants in vases and containers increase the vitality of plants under the influence of adverse environmental factors, such as gas, dust, etc. As a rule, trees on the sidewalks are planted in a row in special left holes. The diameter of the holes should be at least 1.5 m. Planting trees between sidewalks and paths can be combined not only with flower beds and flower beds, but also with lawns (Fig. 4).

Figure 1. Appearance of city roads in greening:

a- trees, shrubs and lawns, b- herbaceous flowering plants in vases and containers, c- main types of seedlings

A combination of flower beds, flower beds and lawns. In such cases, the width of the green line should not exceed 2 m. The distance between trees is usually at least 4 m. It is desirable to create a row of trees from representatives of the same species or one decorative form. It should be remembered that drivers of vehicles must always have a clear view. Placement of trees and shrubs, especially at intersections and street bends, should not interfere with the visibility of pedestrians and vehicle drivers and the movement of vehicles. The height of plants should not exceed 0.6-0.8 m within the so-called "view triangle".

The visibility triangle is calculated based on the speed and braking of vehicles: a corresponding drawing is made, it is placed in the street intersection improvement plan [4]. Another important condition is the provision of street ventilation, which is achieved by regulating the distance between the trees in the rows.

Planting in the streets has its own characteristics and must meet specific requirements, the main of which are gas resistance, noise and dust protection. With this in mind, the following types of plants are recommended: tree species resistant to toxic gas (straight spruce; common chestnut; white acacia, Japanese sophora, honey locust, ailanthus); - gas-resistant types of bushes (honeysuckle, mackerel, medium spirea); - trees that help reduce noise (thorny spruce, western thuja), species of deciduous woody plants that maintain a dense crown (oak, linden, chestnut), shrubs (privet, viburnum, spirea); - types of woody plants with the ability to protect the area from dust, with a dense crown, rough wrinkled leaves (rough pine, maple, ash, horse chestnut, angustifolia, lilac, elder). The choice of plant composition also depends on the orientation of the streets to the main directions, besides, the green areas should not cover the architecture of the buildings. When choosing an assortment of trees and shrubs, you should avoid woody plant species that have superficial root systems that can damage the surface of sidewalks. Using different forms of plants, you can create artistic compositions according to the tasks. When landscaping areas near architectural ensembles and monuments, plant forms that harmoniously blend with the silhouette of the building or monument itself should be used. The seriousness of the individual representative sections of the streets is achieved by the geometric methods of floral design on the plane (in the form of a circle, ellipse, square, rectangle) in combination with low cut borders of bushes.

A more interesting assortment is used to beautify the central streets, reflecting the unique appearance of the streets. Green areas have a positive effect on the climate of cities, enrich the atmosphere with oxygen (for example, one hectare of urban green spaces emits 200 kg of oxygen per day on average) [5], and protect the soil. protects against erosion, drying up

of water sources and pollution. They have a positive effect on the radiation and heat regime and thus create ventilation of the areas, which is very necessary considering the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan. In a word, the health of the city depends on the plants, and the more there are, the more comfortable the climate. According to environmental scientists, the ratio of cities and green spaces should not be less than 1/5 [6]. In this way, I would like to emphasize once again the importance of green areas in the improvement and beautification of streets and roads. Pay close attention to the "neighborhood" of various connections and networks, so as not to harm the aesthetics and life of plants. From properly selected trees and shrubs, landscapers adhere to the rules of plant growth and care (moisture-loving, shade-tolerant, etc.), microclimate conditions, and decorative features (open crown, fruits, scents, etc.) must be observed. In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that "Great things are done with great means. Nature itself creates great things in vain." (A. Herzen)

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